

Material Characterization Improvement in High Temperature Rectangular Waveguide Measurements

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Abstract — The scattering parameters of a single-top gap partially filled rectangular waveguide (PFW) are calculated using mode-matching of the transverse fields. This is accomplished by including in the calculations the complex power contained in higher-order TM^y modes scattered by a material sample in the waveguide. Furthermore, use of the forward and reverse scattering parameters eliminates the dependence of the placement of the sample with respect to a reference or calibration plane. A combination of the higher-order mode-matching and the reference plane independent (RPI) technique provides the best method for overcoming errors associated with high temperature waveguide measurements. Experimental results are presented to validate the analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic characterization of materials is frequently performed at high temperatures, a process that can introduce significant sources of error into the determination of the material properties. The primary deviations from the ideal transmission/reflection measurement scenario involve thermal expansion of the waveguide, which can lead to gaps between the sample and the waveguide walls, and longitudinal shifting of the sample under test. Neglecting these physical changes leads to an inaccurate determination of relative permittivity (ϵ_r) and permeability (μ_r) when the well-known Nicolson-Ross-Weir (NRW) algorithm is employed. The reason for this is twofold. NRW uses only the dominant TE^{10} mode to extract ϵ_r and μ_r , while a partially filled waveguide (PFW) scatters higher-order modes. Also, NRW requires that the distance from the sample under test to the calibration plane be known exactly, which is often impossible to determine during a high temperature test. It will be shown that both of these sources of error can be mitigated so as to correctly extract the electromagnetic properties of the sample under test.

Other researchers have suggested the use of conducting paste to fill gaps, although such a solution could not withstand a high-temperature test [1]. Furthermore, justification of the tangential

field matching done by Jarem *et al* [2] is expounded upon in recently completed work [3], which also extends the analysis to include paramagnetic materials.

2 THEORY

2.1 Partially Filled Waveguide

Consider a rectangular waveguide ($a \approx 2b$), partially filled with a material sample of thickness d and height h , as in Figure 1. Notice the sample is partially filled in the y axis. It is therefore convenient to pursue development of the scattered modes using TM^y modes, as suggested by [4, 5].

Figure 1: Partially Filled Waveguide (PFW), with sample having thickness d and height h .

Fields are generated using the magnetic vector potential A_y . An $e^{j\omega t}$ time dependence is assumed and suppressed. The fields in the empty portions of the waveguide ($z < 0, z > d$) are well known, being of the form

$$\begin{aligned} e_x &= \frac{-k_x k_{y,n}}{j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0} \cos k_x x \sin k_{y,n} y \\ e_y &= \frac{(k_0^2 - k_{y,n}^2)}{j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0} \sin k_x x \cos k_{y,n} y \\ e_z &= \frac{k_{y,n} \gamma_0}{j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0} \sin k_x x \sin k_{y,n} y \\ h_x &= \frac{\gamma_0}{\mu_0} \sin k_x x \cos k_{y,n} y \\ h_y &= 0 \\ h_z &= \frac{k_x}{\mu_0} \cos k_x x \cos k_{y,n} y \end{aligned}$$

such that the mode index n is zero for the dominant mode and a positive integer for all scattered modes. Fields in the partially filled region ($0 < z < d$) are constructed using different vector potentials A_{y1} (material region) and A_{y2} (gap region), respectively. Equating the tangential components of the

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electric and magnetic fields at $y = h$, the planar boundary between the two materials, leads to the following relations for the n^{th} mode:

$$\frac{k_{y1}}{\epsilon_1} \tan k_{y1}h + \frac{k_{y2}}{\epsilon_2} \tan k_{y2}(b-h)h = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\gamma_n^2 = k_{y1,n}^2 + k_x^2 - k^2 = k_{y2,n}^2 + k_x^2 - k_0^2 \quad (1b)$$

where $k_{yi,n}$ ($i = 1, 2$) are the y -directed wavenumbers in the material and gap regions, respectively, k_x is the wavenumber in the x dimension, k is the wavenumber in the material region, k_0 is the wavenumber in the gap region, and γ_n is the PFW propagation constant along the guiding axis. This eigenvalue equation must be solved using numerical techniques, such as the Newton-Raphson root search algorithm.

Continuity of the total tangential \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} fields is enforced at the transverse interfacial boundary between the empty and partially filled regions of the waveguide at $z = 0$ and $z = d$ after truncating the infinite number of scattered modes to N and normalizing with respect to the excitation TM_{10}^y mode, leading to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_{10} + \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \Gamma_n \mathbf{e}_{1n} &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} t_n \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{1n} + \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} r_n \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{1n} \\ \mathbf{h}_{10} - \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \Gamma_n \mathbf{h}_{1n} &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} t_n \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{1n} - \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} r_n \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{1n} \\ \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} t_n \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{1n} e^{-\gamma_n d} + \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} r_n \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{1n} e^{\gamma_n d} &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} T_n \mathbf{e}_{1n} \\ \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} t_n \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{1n} e^{-\gamma_n d} - \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} r_n \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{1n} e^{\gamma_n d} &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} T_n \mathbf{h}_{1n} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The use of the tilde (\sim) indicates the piecewise nature of the field vectors in the PFW region. The system of (2) is ill-posed, having $4N$ unknown variables (Γ_n, r_n, t_n, T_n) and only 4 equations. Applying the testing function $\cos \frac{p\pi y}{b}$ ($p=0, \dots, N-1$) and integrating over the guide cross section yields a well-posed system consisting of $4N$ equations and $4N$ unknown variables in the form $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{B}$, where \mathbf{B} is the forcing function and \mathbf{x} is the solution space of unknown variables.

The solution γ_n of (1a) is used to populate the system of (2), which can be inverted to calculate the dominant reflection (Γ_1) and transmission (T_1) coefficients, which are identically equal to the theoretical scattering parameters S_{11}^{thy} and S_{21}^{thy} . Given an initial guess of ϵ_r and μ_r , a two-dimensional iterative root search minimizes the absolute difference between the theoretical (thy) S-parameters and the

experimental (exp) S-parameters obtained from the network analyzer:

$$\begin{aligned} |S_{11}^{thy} - S_{11}^{exp}| &< tol \\ |S_{21}^{thy} - S_{21}^{exp}| &< tol \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The values of ϵ_r and μ_r which force the equations in (3) below a specified tolerance (tol) leads to the desired parameters of the sample under test.

2.2 Reference Plane Independence (RPI)

Dependence on sample location with respect to the reference plane can be eliminated by using minimization equations that use both the forward and reverse S-parameters, as has been suggested in [6]. When combined with the PFW analysis of the previous section, the minimization equations become

$$\begin{aligned} |S_{11}^{thy} S_{22}^{thy} - S_{11}^{exp} S_{22}^{exp}| &< tol \\ |S_{21}^{thy} S_{12}^{thy} - S_{21}^{exp} S_{12}^{exp}| &< tol \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The reverse S-parameters ($S_{22}^{thy}, S_{12}^{thy}$) are identically equal to the forward S-parameters ($S_{11}^{thy}, S_{21}^{thy}$) calculated in Section 2.1, which helps to minimize computation. It must be noted that use of RPI in material characterization assumes sample homogeneity. If the sample is not sufficiently uniform, the resultant parameter extraction will be flawed.

3 TEST PROCEDURE

Characterization of a commercially available magnetic shielding material was performed at S-band (2.6 – 3.95 GHz). A Thru-Reflect-Line (TRL) calibration was performed on the network analyzer system. Samples were cut to the specifications found in Table 1. Measurements were performed at room temperature using gap scenarios that simulated high-temperature tests.

Sample #	Height	Gap
1	1.340 [in]	0 [mils]
2	1.313 [in]	27 [mils]
3	1.259 [in]	81 [mils]

Table 1: Material Samples, S-Band. All samples are 2.84 (in) wide and 125 mils thick. Sample 1 is the reference (i.e., the fully-filled result).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Characterization

The characterization improvement, including RPI, when applied to Sample 2 corrects the value of ϵ' to within 5% of the true value (i.e., the fully-filled NRW result), as seen in Figure 2; imaginary data is not shown, as the material is nearly electrically lossless. The correction is accomplished using 10 modes, i.e. the dominant and 9 higher-order TM^y modes. The significance of overcoming a 27 mil gap cannot be understated. Improvement in the measurement of μ_r , also using a 10 mode correction, is displayed in Figures 3 and 4. By inspection, it is clear from the difference between the Initial and TRUE traces that a PFW has less effect on calculation of permeability. Accordingly, the correction algorithm does not significantly improve the measurement.

Figure 2: ϵ' of Sample 2 characterized at S-band. Corrected measurement compensates for the errors of the initial PFW measurement.

Errors introduced by the larger gap size of 81 mils are also mitigated by the improvement techniques. The characterization of ϵ' of Sample 3 is given in Figure 5, where it can be seen that a 10 mode correction yields a satisfactory result. Magnetic behavior, both in error and correction, at this gap size is similar to that of Figure 3, and is thus not repeated.

4.2 Propagation Wavenumber

The behavior of the higher-order modes in the region of the PFW can be investigated through use of the propagation-attenuation ratio $\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right)$. This is the ratio of the real and imaginary parts of the propagation wavenumber γ_n of each mode. A PFW

Figure 3: μ' of Sample 2 characterized at S-band.

Figure 4: μ'' of Sample 2 characterized at S-band.

Figure 5: ϵ' of Sample 3 at S-band.

with a small gap will more closely resemble a fully-filled waveguide, causing the dominant mode to be “strongly” dominant, whereas a PFW with a moderate to large gap will not have this characteristic. This behavior can be verified in Table 2, where a comparison of the $\frac{\alpha}{\beta}$ ratios of the first 5 modes is shown.

Mode #	Sample 2 $\frac{\alpha}{\beta}$	Sample 3 $\frac{\alpha}{\beta}$
1	0.3	2.1
2	9.8	3.0
3	46.4	4.4
4	115.7	6.0
5	164.6	8.0

Table 2: Propagation - Attenuation Ratios of first 5 modes of Samples 2 & 3.

5 CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that electromagnetic characterization of a partially-filled waveguide (PFW) sample, such as would often be found in a high-temperature scenario, can be improved through the use of higher-order modes and a reference plane independent technique. The combination of these two methods improve on the NRW algorithm by calculating the theoretical S-parameters while considering the complex power coupled into higher-order modes, and eliminating the phase shift caused by improper placement and/or movement of the sample in the waveguide. Although the tests were performed at room temperature, the method is valid for use at high temperatures. It was also observed that a y -directed PFW had more adverse effects on the extraction of permittivity rather than permeability, as physically expected for a y -directed excitation. Future work will include the investigation of other gap scenarios.

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